

DETERMINING COMPOSITE CONSTITUENT CONTENT IN NATURAL FIBRE COMPOSITES USING NIR SPECTROSCOPY

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1 Introduction

In composite manufacturing it is often necessary to determine the composite constituent proportions after a part has been fabricated e.g. for reverse engineering design or quality assurance. This is performed by resin burn-off testing for glass reinforced parts and by acid digestion for carbon reinforced parts. Neither of these methods is suitable to determine constituent proportions of natural fibre reinforced composites in post-production parts due to the biological nature of the material.

Near infrared (NIR) spectroscopy is a chemometric method for determining the electromagnetic radiation absorption spectrum of a particular material. In this study it was proposed that NIR spectroscopy could be used to decipher the constituents of ground (particulate size ≤ 0.20 mm) natural fibre thermoset laminates. The study was comprised of three primary aspects: a preliminary investigation to determine the capabilities and limitations of NIR spectroscopy to identify individual constituents and measure their proportions, development of an optimized procedure for sampling and appropriate regression factor selection, and finally the creation of two NIR prediction models: one to predict the percent content of a common fire retardant filler in resin and one to predict the fibre content of a natural fibre composite.

2 Materials, Sampling and Equipment

Materials included polyester, vinyl ester and epoxy thermoset resins, three forms of natural fibre nonwoven composite matting and common composite fillers including alumina trihydrate (ATH), phosphorus and wood flour. Samples were produced by Vacuum assisted Resin Transfer Moulding (VaRTM) with an adjustable cavity to

control fibre volume content. Neat resin and resin-filler specimens were cast in open air under ambient conditions. The Polychromix Phazir, a portable NIR scanner, was used to measure the NIR absorbance of the ground samples. The Phazir measures the intensity of infrared light reflected at 100 discrete wavelengths spaced equally between 1596 nm and 2396 nm [1].

3 Model Creation and Validation

A preliminary principal component analysis (PCA) study was performed to qualitatively analyze the spectral difference between the individual constituents. Following this initial evaluation, a partial least squares (PLS) regression was used to create a prediction model from a set of calibration samples to correlate the weight fraction of ATH filler in resin to its NIR spectrum. ASTM E1655 suggests that the maximum number of PLS factors which can be used to create a PLS model is dependent upon the number of calibration samples available [2]:

$$\begin{aligned} k \leq 3 &\rightarrow n=24 \\ k > 3 &\rightarrow n=6(k+1) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where n is the number of calibration samples and k is the number of PLS factors

A PLS model based on 2 PLS factors was created from 24 calibration samples as recommended in ASTM E1655. Although this model performed well, further investigation revealed that PLS models can be created from fewer samples while maintaining the same level of performance [3]. The immediate benefit of this is the reduced time and cost associated with sample creation and preparation.

Esbensen [3] proposes an iterative approach in which the number of calibration samples and PLS factors are varied, the model tested against a validation set of samples, and this process repeated until an acceptable level of model prediction accuracy and precision are met. Figure 1 shows that for a simple model to predict the ATH content in thermoset resin, a model created with five samples performs comparably with a model created with twenty-five samples when one or two PLS factors are used.

Figure 1. Model performance as a function of PLS factors and number of samples used to create the prediction model. As the number of PLS factors is increased, a higher number of samples are required to maintain the level of statistical performance.

Based on this iterative approach, PLS models were created to predict the percent weight content of ATH and fibre content in natural fibre composites. Each model was tested against a set of validation samples and the model's performance evaluated based on its statistical accuracy and precision.

Model accuracy was measured by the bias as defined by equation (2). Model precision was measured by

the standard error of prediction (SEP) as defined by equation (3). Root mean squared error of prediction (RMSEP) was used as an overall measure of error, and is defined by equation (4).

$$Bias = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_{i,val} - y_{i,val}) \quad (2)$$

$$SEP = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_{i,val} - y_{i,val} - Bias)^2} \quad (3)$$

$$RMSEP = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_{i,val} - y_{i,val})^2} \quad (4)$$

$$RMSEP^2 \approx SEP^2 + Bias^2 \quad (5)$$

$n \rightarrow$ # of measurements
 $\hat{y}_{i,val} \rightarrow$ predicted value
 $y_{i,val} \rightarrow$ reference value

4 Results

4.1 Preliminary Work

Preliminary work was done to assess the suitability of using NIR spectroscopy to differentiate between the different constituent components of natural fibre composites.

Figure 2 shows a graph of the first two components of a PCA analysis of several distinct samples of filler, fibre, and thermoset resin. Figure 2 shows that these constituent types can be separated due to their distinct NIR spectra. Based on this preliminary assessment, it was concluded that a PLS model could be made to accurately predict the fibre and/or filler content of a natural fibre composite material.

Figure 2. PCA of individual constituents using two principal components.

4.2 ATH Model

Based on the results of the preliminary study, a model for predicting the weight fraction of ATH in a cured thermoset resin was created. A PLS model was created from 25 calibration samples with ATH contents ranging from 0 to 65 pph by weight and validated with an additional 6 samples.

The calibration and validation sample sets for the ATH model were designed based on the recommendations in ASTM E1655 [2]. In order to test the validity of the rule of thumb suggested in the ASTM standard, PLS models were created from 2, 5, and 25 calibration samples. Model performance was then evaluated using a common set of validation samples. The RMSEP for each model is graphed in Figure 1 as a function of the number of PLS factors used to create each model. Figure 1 shows several prominent trends: First, since the physical system being modeled contains only 2 distinct components (resin and ATH) and since these components have little chemical deviation as shown by independent NIR sampling, very few samples are required to make accurate PLS models. This is illustrated by the fact that the model created from just 2 calibration samples and a single PLS factor gives an acceptably low RMSEP of ~1.5%.

Figure 3 shows the RMSEP, Bias, and SEP for the ATH-25 model as a function of the number of PLS factors.

Figure 3. RMSEP, Bias and SEP of ATH prediction model created from 25 samples.

Note that the RMSEP (combined measurement of accuracy and precision) remains relatively constant over the full range of PLS factors. However, the magnitude of the bias tends to increase while the SEP decreases as the number of PLS factors increases. Overall, increasing the number of PLS factors above an optimal point is shown in this case to produce a more precise but less accurate model. This exemplifies the dangers of relying solely on the RMSEP to provide the best PLS model for a given data set. Typically, deficiencies in precision can be overcome by increasing the number of scans of a sample, a strategy that is relatively quick when dealing with NIR testing. Deficiencies in accuracy, however, cannot be overcome even in theory since an infinite number of tests will still give an incorrect answer, where the degree of incorrectness depends on the magnitude of the bias. Therefore, it is recommended that the RMSEP and the Bias be considered when choosing an optimal PLS model, and the SEP used to ensure that an adequate number of NIR scans are performed on each sample.

4.3 Hemp Fibre Model

Based on the knowledge gained in the preliminary NIR evaluation and ATH-resin spectral modeling, a

second NIR model was created to predict the volume fraction of hemp fibre in a thermoset composite. Based on the work of Esbensen [3] as well as the experience gained by building the ATH model, it was decided to build the hemp fibre model from a relatively small number of calibration samples, and to increase the number of samples if the RMSEP and Bias were deemed to be unacceptably high. The PLS model was created using 4 calibration samples with fibre volume contents between 0% and 26%. Two validation samples were created with fibre volume contents of 11% and 21%. Figure 4 shows the predicted hemp content compared to the known hemp content for both of the validation samples.

Figure 4. Predicted hemp content compared to reference

The best fit line in Figure 4 shows that the average predicted and reference values are quite close, giving it a low overall bias. However, caution should be used in assuming that a low overall bias equates to low prediction bias for all possible samples. Figure 4 shows that the absolute bias for the two validation samples are on the order of 1% - 2%, which are acceptable, but still considerably higher than the overall absolute bias of 0.2%.

Figure 5 presents the statistical error as a function of the number of PLS factors used from the evaluation of the two validation samples.

Figure 5. Statistical Performance of the hemp fibre prediction model created from calibration 4 samples

Based on the data in Figure 5 a model was created with 3 PLS factors. This model was chosen to minimize the bias while keeping the SEP and RMSEP acceptably low.

Additional validation samples were also created with either an alternate resin or an alternate fibre to which the fibre-resin model was created. The composition of these samples is shown in Table 1.

Validation			
Sample	Resin	Fibre	V _{Flax}
Flax-VE	Vinyl Ester	Flax	10.8%
	Vinyl Ester	Flax	22.4%
Kenaf-VE	Vinyl Ester	Kenaf	10.3%
	Vinyl Ester	Kenaf	18.9%
Hemp-P	Polyester	Hemp	10.8%
	Polyester	Hemp	22.2%
Hemp-VE2	Vinyl Ester 2	Hemp	10.5%
	Vinyl Ester 2	Hemp	21.6%

Table 1. Summary of the additional validation samples used.

The purpose of these additional validations was to evaluate how the model performs when used to test samples of differing constituents than what was used to create the model. Figure 6 shows a summary of the error when using the hemp fibre NIR model to predict natural fibre content in composites consisting of alternate natural fibres or thermoset resins.

Figure 6. RMSEP, Bias and SEP for the extended validation of the Hemp/Vinyl Ester PLS model. Extended validation evaluated the statistical error of the hemp model when used to measure the fibre content of 4 alternate sample composite compositions.

Of the 4 additional validation samples tested, the model performed the best on the Flax-VE samples. Both the precision and the error for the Flax-VE samples were roughly the same as for the original Hemp-VE validation samples. The poor performance of the model on the remaining three additional validation samples indicate that the model itself is only valid for the constituent contents in which the model itself was created. This confirms the best practices as suggested by Esbensen [3] that a PLS model only be used to evaluate constituent components for which it was calibrated.

5 Conclusions

- NIR spectroscopy was found to be a useful tool for distinguishing between different components of natural fibre composites.
- Two PLS models were created from NIR spectra, one to predict ATH content in a thermoset resin, and one to predict hemp fibre content in a specific vinyl ester thermoset.
- The number of samples and number of PLS factors were iterated to create an optimized PLS model.

PLS model performance was evaluated using validation samples to estimate each model's accuracy and precision as shown in

- Table 2.

Model	Bias	SEP	RMSEP
ATH-VE	-0.41%	1.27%	1.34%
Hemp-VE	-0.19%	2.14%	2.15%

Table 2. Summary of the accuracy and precision of the two PLS models created

- PLS models are only valid for identifying constituent proportions of materials for which they were calibrated.

References

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